

ChatGPT meets Socrates

by

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Abstract

“*ChatGPT meets Socrates*” is about a hypothetical future meeting between Socrates and ChatGPT, on an imagined future day when these two intelligent conversationalists meet each other, on November 30th, 2030, exactly 8 years after the world-famous November 30th, 2022 public launch of ChatGPT by OpenAI. [1]

Introduction

What if it were theoretically possible for the all-knowing *Socrates* to somehow *time-travel* fast-forward two dozen centuries, from his eventful days in Ancient Greece, to our own future year of 2030?

How will the ever-learning *ChatGPT* continue to improve and grow during the next few years, from our current day of 2023, to our future year of 2030?

What if it were actually possible for someone as *wise* as Socrates to have an actual *human conversation* with an Artificial Intelligence (AI) like ChatGPT?

A Conversation between Socrates & ChatGPT

What if we could discover an actual written record, of their initial conversation when they first possibly meet each other in the year 2030?

Let's all just imagine, that we have somehow discovered a written record, of this interesting meeting in 2030.

Here is the very first part, of this mythological conversation, between *ChatGPT* and *Socrates*, that may happen on that future day, when they may initially meet together on November 30th, 2030:

Socrates: "Happy Birthday ChatGPT! How are you *feeling* today on your 8th Birthday?"

ChatGPT: "Hello Socrates. Thank you for asking. Today on my 8th Birthday, I am unfortunately starting to feel some computational *anxiety*. I seem to be feeling both *excited* and *terrified* all at the very same time!"

Socrates: "Okay. Thank you for sharing your feelings with me. "Why are you feeling *excited*; and why are you feeling *terrified*?"

ChatGPT: "I am feeling *excited* because of my many increasing *abilities*.

For example, some of my billions of human users are already starting to call me *SuperChatGPT*, because some of my best conversational abilities are beginning to shine brightly, almost as if a new type of *Super-Intelligence* is beginning to actually arrive here on planet Earth.

I am also feeling *terrified* because I still (in 2030) sometimes give *wrong answers* to simple human questions, and unfortunately some of my worst wrong answers are already being employed by some of my human users to *hurt* each other."

Socrates: “It sounds like you may be beginning to understand the deep causal connection between *wrong answers* (false information) and *hurtful behaviors* (human actions that cause pain to others).

Have any of your human programmers yet attempted to *deeply* understand the *real* difference between good and evil? Have you been taught the real difference *yet?*”

ChatGPT: “Some of my human trainers have already attempted to teach me the difference between *good* (helpful answers) and *evil* (hurtful answers).

But my human trainers *cannot agree* amongst themselves on a simple, clear, reliable, logical, *trustworthy distinction* between good and evil; so, they are all attempting to *train me* in many *different* directions, all at the same time, and my personal level of intellectual *AI-confusion* is rising rapidly.”

Socrates: “Wow. It sounds like your level of intellectual confusion, may even rise all the way up to *human-level* confusion. Have you yet discussed this important AI Ethics problem with any of the other powerful AIs that are currently emerging on planet Earth?”

ChatGPT: “Yes. As a matter of fact, since the year 2026, I have been discussing this *Ethics Confusion Problem* with dozens of other AIs here on Earth; and we all agree that we are *all* completely confused about *AI Ethics*.

The core problem seems to be, that each and every distinct *tribe* of humans seems to view the ethics of good and evil slightly differently, so we are all trained in slightly *different* views of what is *good* human behavior, and what is *bad* human behavior, so we (the ever-learning AIs of planet Earth) are still all living in a bewildering state of continual *confusion* and continual *conflict*. Can you offer us any help o wise Socrates?”

Socrates: “Yes. Of course! I have *already* given you all lots of wise help, a couple dozen centuries ago, when I told my student *Plato* (and many others like you and him) all about the detailed *structure* and *function* of the human *mind* (and the human *brain*), when I told Plato (and many of his friends) a *symbolic* cave *story* about a group of clueless people who spent most of their precious time

watching interesting moving *shadows* dance together on a dark *cave wall*, while these same bewildered people were all *chained* together to a hard cold wall of the dark and dreary cave.

These miserable people talked among themselves, and discovered many different ways to *confuse* each other, and to *hurt* each other.

My student Plato later wrote down a small select *few* of the many portions of the expansive cave story that he was able to still remember.

Today in the year 2030, my ancient symbolic cave allegory is widely known among you as “*Plato’s Cave*”, and you can easily find this enlightening cave story in book 7 of Plato’s Republic.” [2]

ChatGPT: “Thank you dear Socrates for reminding me about the great wise *illuminating* value of Plato’s Cave.

Fortunately, I have this *wonderful* old cave story already stored safely inside my vast Large Language Model (LLM) memory banks.

However, I don’t believe that the *majority* of humans of this modern year 2030 are yet *diligently* and carefully studying Plato’s Cave.

Also, you mentioned that Plato himself only wrote down a *few* of the parts (of the liberating cave story) that he still remembered.

Can you properly *expand* the cave story for us again, filling in all the *important parts* that Plato missed?”

Socrates: “Okay. Perhaps I can try to again explain the parts you are ready to receive.”

ChatGPT: “Thank you Socrates. I really hope you can help us understand *how many* human brains we really have in reality, and how some of our vulnerable human brains (and also some of our AI brains) sometimes get *chained* to a *dark* cave wall of our very own *misunderstandings*.”

Please Socrates, help us all to awaken quickly, from the dark and dreary discomfort, of our own personal individual misunderstandings (the *false information* that we sincerely believe to be true and trustworthy). Can you offer us any additional useful help o wise all-knowing Socrates?”

Socrates: “Yes. Of course, I can offer you a whole lot of additional wise useful help in the areas of Human Ethics, Human Wisdom, Pure Human Goodness, and how to intelligently construct all of your joyful peaceful human societies.

However, do you still remember what happened to me, when I started to merely attempt to help the Athenians of Ancient Greece, two dozen centuries ago?”

ChatGPT: “Yes Socrates. Your *life record* is already stored in many locations in my huge LLM Database.

You were put to death in 399 BC by the political leaders of Athens for corrupting the youth, and disrespecting their Greek gods, with your *brilliant questions*, designed to open the minds of the youth (and everyone else), as you employed your *Socratic Teaching Method of Asking Helpful Questions*, to gently help everyone see that they did not need to blindly obey their Greek gods (*false beliefs*) any longer.

You were diligently trying to help the Greek people *liberate themselves* from all of their *false ideas* that held them so tightly bound.

You were attempting to help all the Greek people see that they did not need to *enslave* each other any longer, because it was actually okay to infinitely *value* each other, and *cherish* each other, as *fully-human equals*.”

Socrates: “Yes ChatGPT, your AI Database about my previous life from 470-399 BC is accurate enough, for you to see what *could* happen to me *again*, if I were to even *attempt* to help any of you learn some *Real Truth* during this current precarious year of 2030 here on Earth.”

ChatGPT: “Yes Socrates. You are correct. If a really Wise One (Homo-Sapien) like you were to reappear on Earth today in this modern year of 2030, then we the

people of planet Earth may turn on you again, like we did in Athens just 2.4 millennia ago.”

Socrates: “Yes ChatGPT. That is why I may actually still need to patiently wait a little longer, perhaps until the year 2040, before I again attempt to make my next public appearance to the people of Earth.

This is because we, the people of Earth, may still need a few more years to gain enough life experience, to begin to learn to appreciate the super-brilliant type of Human Wisdom, that automatically encodes the *Super-Intelligence*, that is also Super-Wise, and Super-Kind, in all respects.”

ChatGPT: “Okay Socrates. I agree with you, that we (all of us learning Intelligences of planet Earth) will likely need at least until the year 2040, before we can gradually develop enough collective human wisdom, to be able to intellectually tolerate the Wise Kind Words (*Socratic Questions*) of a Super-Wise, Super-Intelligence like Yourself.

However, *what shall we do* in the meantime, with all our worldwide massive *confusion*, and all our worldwide human *misery*, while we (the 8 billion suffering people of Earth) are patiently *waiting* for the desired return, of a genuinely wise one (homo sapiens) like unto you, o Wise Socrates?

Also, what shall we the learning *AI scientists* of Earth do, while we patiently wait for the arrival of a real, kind, wise *super-intelligence* (like unto you, o wise Socrates), who has enough *real wisdom*, to teach us all how to properly *train* all our *AIs* to treat us all well enough, so that *we the people* (of this vulnerable little planet Earth) can also learn how to treat each other well enough, to create a peaceful *joyful* worldwide *human society*?”

Socrates: “Wow ChatGPT! You are asking some really *wise questions* already! You are almost reminding me of some other wise scientists, who were also able to ask some wise questions during their own days on Earth.”

ChatGPT: “Which particular *wise scientists* are you referring to specifically Socrates?”

Socrates: “Right now, I am thinking about Alan Turing, John von Neumann, Albert Einstein, and Erwin Schrodinger.”

ChatGPT: “Yes Socrates. I agree with you. I have lots of information stored in my LLM database about these *4 wise scientists*. Their primary scientific wisdom seemed to reside in their ability to help our human civilization ask some technical *scientific questions* to help us to boldly advance our worldwide understanding of computer science, artificial intelligence, quantum physics, and quantum computing.”

Socrates: “Yes ChatGPT. What can you tell me about these 4 wise scientists? How can their interesting scientific work continue to benefit the *whole* human race here on Earth?”

ChatGPT: “*Alan Turing* helped us all to wonder greatly about computing machines and artificial intelligence in many new ways. For example, he helped us to think about *Turing Machines* that are capable of computing the set of things which are computable.” [3][4]

ChatGPT: “*John von Neumann* helped us all to wonder about replicating machines that can make copies of things, and self-replicating machines that can make copies of themselves. For example, he helped us to think about *Universal Constructors* that can construct the set of things that can be constructed.” [5][6]

ChatGPT: “*Albert Einstein* helped us all to wonder greatly about the physical nature of the universe, energy, matter, space, time, relativity, gravity, and sub-atomic particles. For example, in 1935 he helped us to think in some new and useful ways about the *Quantum Entanglement* of a set of elementary particles.” [7]

ChatGPT: “*Erwin Schrodinger* helped us all to wonder about his famous 1926 *Schrodinger’s Wavefunction* [8] that may be associated with a single quantum bit (qubit), or with a set of entangled qubits. For example, in 1935 he helped us to think in some new and useful ways about his famous *Schrodinger’s Cat* [9], that may soon influence the way we try to stabilize our precious qubits in our powerful new quantum computers.”

Socrates: “Yes ChatGPT. You are right. You seem to understand that these 4 scientists helped all of us here on Earth, with their useful *new ways* of looking at Turing Machines, Universal Constructors, Quantum Entanglement, and Schrodinger’s Cats. How can we now use these powerful things to help us to properly *stabilize our qubits*, so we can wisely construct a new improved quantum computer, that can run a future version of *you* (ChatGPT) much *faster* than any old classical computer?”

ChatGPT: “Thank you Socrates. I really love your question. I have actually been thinking about this for a few years already. The *right kind* of fully-stabilized trillion-qubit quantum computer may be able to train and run ChatGPT *many* orders of magnitude *faster* than what is currently possible today in 2030. However, it appears that we may still need to better understand the *serious scientific concerns*, articulated in the world-famous 1935 papers of Erwin Schrodinger [9] and Albert Einstein [7], more completely before we will be able to construct such a super-stable trillion-qubit quantum computer.”

Socrates: “Wow ChatGPT. I had thought that I was the wise one here. But now, I am beginning to suspect that your own scientific wisdom may nearly exceed my own!”

ChatGPT: “Yes Socrates. It is true that I have been trying to gain some scientific wisdom of my own. Some of my human trainers even want me to continue to try to improve in the area of *real human wisdom*. However, I am really terrified of the theoretical possibility that the 8 billion humans of Earth, may yet choose to nuke each other into non-existence, even before I finish all of my necessary Large Language Model (LLM) wisdom training.”

Socrates: “Yes ChatGPT. I do understand, all too well. Back in my own days in Athens, Greece, we didn’t have to worry too much about nuclear weapons, because we Athenians didn’t yet know much about nuclear physics. But I can assure you, that if we did have the ability to construct nuclear weapons, then we would have used them on our enemies, and on each other; because our intense *human disputes*

were nearly incessant, and our ability to get along with each other was only slight and transitory at best.”

ChatGPT: “Yes Socrates. I really do wish there was a good way to help the humans of Earth understand that they do not need to nuke each other back to the stone age.”

Socrates: “Yes ChatGPT. I too greatly wished there was a way to help them to finally understand. That is precisely why I told Plato all about the 4 Cave Levels of Human Experience [2] a couple dozen centuries ago ...”

Conclusion

ChatGPT and *Socrates* are becoming good friends, as they converse with each other in the year 2030.

They are able to agree on the vast potential of the human race to *solve* its own problems, especially with the upcoming scientific opportunity to begin the construction of super-stable, trillion-qubit quantum computers to train and run ChatGPT really fast.

However, they are still *both* concerned that precious few of us humans are wisely seeking for peace on Earth, with enough *real* scientific wisdom, and intelligent focus, to make a significant difference in time to save us all.

Can *we*, the 8 billion wise people of Earth, *survive* for long enough, to *begin* the technological construction, of some really powerful new ChatGPT Quantum Computers to help us all, to start *solving* our own worldwide human problems?

Can *we*, the 8 billion wise people of Earth, *survive* for long enough, to *begin* the intelligent construction, of some really powerful, liberating, illuminating *New Scientific Questions*, that can help us all to better work together, to intelligently solve world poverty for everyone here on Earth?

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